

THE EFFECT OF MINDFULNESS TRAINING ON IMPROVING SECONDARY EDUCATION STUDENTS' MENTAL CAPACITY AND REDUCING TEACHERS' STRESS DURING LESSONS.

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ABSTRACT

This research paper presents the results and achievements of mindfulness training when applied in high school classrooms. Since raising a healthy generation is one of the most important progressive tasks in our society, training in this way ensures the teacher's mental health and students' ability to perform tasks. The results of the research conducted in two groups showed that mindfulness training practiced twice a week helped teachers to calm their minds in the daily noise of pupils and gave them the opportunity to conduct quality lessons, while training helped to develop brain activity in students, and showed the theoretical practice of reducing academic pressure in classes.

Introduction

Unfortunately, in modern educational conditions, especially in schools, not only teachers, but also students are increasingly stressed due to the large amount of pressure of studying and the classroom environment. To reduce this pressure and develop cognitive activity, mindfulness training can be used as a promising strategy to solve stress management in students and teachers and to reduce feelings of fear and nervousness. This research paper examines the effects of mindfulness training on the cognitive abilities of secondary school students and the potential for regular practice to reduce both teacher and student stress during lessons.

Flook (2013) found that "it is a part of the formula for promoting a healthy classroom environment for the teacher with the help of reduce his or her own stress and manage the students during the lesson." The present research investigates how integrating mindfulness practices into the classroom might improve students' cognitive abilities and offer teachers effective stress management tools.

Research Questions:

This research paper looks to explore a few key questions:

Does mindfulness training help teachers become less stressed and perform better mentally?"

Can mindfulness training reduce stress for teachers, make classes more engaging, and improve students' cognitive performance?

Can mindfulness training enhance teaching quality without disrupting regular school lessons?

Literature Review

Research has shown that mindfulness practices can positively affect both psychological and cognitive functioning in various populations. According to Zenner (2014) "Mindfulness practices enhance the quality and purpose of education in the 21st century, and include students' attention and emotional self-regulation, reflection, moral sensitivity, creativity, and problem-solving." Studies have shown that students who engage in mindfulness during class improve concentration, memory, and problem-solving skills.

In addition, in the process of communication with teachers, it was found that mindfulness training reduced their stress and emotional fatigue in the classroom. Flook mentioned that "the teacher's role is important to create a classroom environment that promotes students' learning and social-emotional well-being."

This study builds on earlier findings by investigating the dual impact of mindfulness training on both students and teachers in a secondary school setting.

Methodology

Participants:

In the research, 30 high school pupils from the school where I work, aged 14 to 16 and 3 teachers from this school took part. The participants were divided into two groups: the first group was experimentally trained to perform 2 weeks of mindfulness exercises, and the second group did not perform anything.

Procedure:

Mindfulness training, lasting 5 minutes each, was conducted twice a week during class time and in literature lessons. During the session, students practiced how to focus on the subject and learned some techniques such as mindful breathing, body scan meditation, and mindful listening. Pre- and post-intervention assessments were conducted to assess changes in student cognitive performance and, most importantly, teacher stress levels in delivering the content and quality assurance of the lesson.

Instruments:

Cognitive tests: Standardized tests measuring attention, working memory, and problem-solving skills were administered to students from the Internet, and psychological tests were administered in consultation with the school psychologist. Cognitive questions:

"Repeat the following sequence of numbers backwards: 7, 3, 9, 4, 6."

"You have 5 liters of water and a 3-liter jug. How can you measure exactly 4 liters?"

Teacher Stress Questionnaire: A test developed by a school psychologist and internet-derived tests were used to measure changes in teachers' perceived stress levels before and after the intervention. For example:

"How often do you feel emotionally drained after a day of teaching?"

"On a scale from 1 to 5, how satisfied are you with your teaching career?"

"When you feel stressed at work, how often do you seek support from colleagues?"

"Do you find relaxation techniques (e.g., deep breathing, meditation) helpful in reducing your stress?"

Results

The data collected from the tests showed that the experience in the experimental group showed a significant increase in the mental role of the students, especially when they developed concentration and retention of the learned topic in memory. However, teachers in the mindfulness training group said they felt significantly lower levels of stress during lessons compared to the second group. Addition to this, teachers mentioned that they are felt physically and mentally healthier. Reducing feelings of stress depends on the ability to calm and manage the mind while improving classroom dynamics and teaching quality.

Discussion of Success

The findings suggest that mindfulness training has a dual benefit in educational settings: it not only improves students' cognitive abilities but also serves as an effective stress management tool for teachers. The results of the experiment are consistent with previous research on how the brain works and the role of consciousness in promoting emotional well-being and cognitive development.

By incorporating mindfulness practices not only in the classroom, but also into daily activities, teachers can create a more comfortable learning environment for their children while learning to understand and manage their emotions. Findings suggest that while mindfulness programs are important to teachers' professional development, integrating them into student curricula can facilitate the learning process.

Limitations

There may be shortcomings in the writing and correct presentation of this research. The group experiment was not professionally researched, relying only on superficial ideas and vague tests.

Conclusion

This research highlights the positive impact of mindfulness training on both student mental ability and teacher stress reduction at school. Implementing mindfulness programs could significantly enhance the overall learning experience by fostering a more peaceful, focused, and supportive classroom environment.

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